

Search for Potent Anthelmintics—Part XV. Azomethines Derived from 2-Phenyl-3-(*p*-aminophenyl)-6, 8-Substituted Quinazolones

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Thirty new 2-phenyl-3-(*p*-arylideneaminophenyl)-6,8-substituted-4-quinazolones have been prepared. Thirteen of them, when screened against *Hymenolepis nana* in mice at a dose of 250 mg/kg, showed significant activity.

A number of azomethines¹⁻³ have gained importance in recent years as potential anthelmintics.

Nitrofurantoin⁴, an azomethine has been particularly known to exhibit significant antifilarial activity against both adult females and microfilariae of *Litomosoides carinni*. Moreover, a few quinazolone derivatives⁵ including 2-benzimidazolylmethylthio-4-quinazolones⁶ have also shown marked anthelmintic activity against *N. dubius* infection in mice. These findings induced us to synthesise the title azomethines with a view to study their anthelmintic efficacy.

p-Phenylene diamine was heated with various substituted anthranils in open air bath to afford 2-phenyl-3-(*p*-aminophenyl)-6,8-substituted-4-quinazolones⁸. The latter were refluxed with different aldehydes in absolute ethanol in the presence of glacial acetic acid to furnish the desired azomethines.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected.

I. 2-Phenyl-3-(*p*-aminophenyl)-6,8-substituted-4-quinazolones :

Equimolar quantities of an appropriately substituted anthranil and *p*-phenylene diamine were heated on a direct flame for 10 minutes. The reaction product was cooled and triturated with ethanol and filtered. The crude solid thus obtained was recrystallized from ethanol. Melting points, yield

and analysis of the prepared compounds are recorded in Table 1.

II. 2-Phenyl-3-(*p*-arylideneaminophenyl)-6,8-substituted-4-quinazolones :

A mixture of 2-phenyl-3-(*p*-aminophenyl)-6,8-substituted-4-quinazolone (0.01 mole), aldehyde (0.01 mole), ethanol (30 ml) and glacial acetic acid (0.5 ml) was refluxed for 4 hours. The resulting mixture was cooled, filtered and excess of ethanol was distilled off from the filtrate. The solid obtained was recrystallised from ethanol (Table 2).

Determination of anthelmintic activity against *H. nana* infection in mice :

In vivo screening was carried out by the method of Steward, with slight modification. Newly weaned mice (25-20 g) were infected with 200 mature viable ova of *H. nana*. On the 15th day the infected animals were starved and treated next day with single oral dose of 250 mg/kg of the compound under test. A group of three animals was used for each of the compounds. Another group of three animals was left untreated as control. All the animals including controls were again starved for 24 hrs before they were sacrificed on the third day after treatment. The small intestine was removed and washed with saline water and worms were collected. The intestine was then pressed in between two glass plates and viewed against light. The worms which could not be removed by washing were counted. All the worms were classified according to their size and scored. The results, thus, obtained were compared with those of control group of animals.

TABLE 1—2-PHENYL-3-(p-AMINOPHENYL)-6,8-SUBSTITUTED-4-QUINAZOLONES*

Sl. No.	X	X'	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Nitrogen%	
						Found	Calcd.
1.	H	H	290	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₂ O	13.08	13.41
2.	Br	H	220	58	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ BrN ₂ O	11.04	10.71
3.	Cl	H	214	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O	12.38	12.09
4.	I	H	180	70	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ IN ₂ O	9.13	9.56
5.	Br	Br	270	52	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ Br ₂ N ₂ O	8.58	8.92

* Showed spectral bands at 1660 to 1670 cm⁻¹ (C=O of quinazolones),
3400 to 3500 cm⁻¹ (-NH- of arom prim. amine).

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	X	X'	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Nitrogen%		%inhibition of <i>H. nana</i> in mice
							Found	Calcd.	
1.*	H	H	C ₆ H ₅	> 300	50	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ N ₂ O	10.06	10.47	—
2.*	H	H	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	> 300	58	C ₂₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O	9.92	9.64	—
3.*	H	H	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	> 300	56	C ₂₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O	9.28	9.64	Inactive
4.*	H	H	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	> 300	62	C ₂₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂	10.87	10.07	Inactive
5.*	H	H	<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	> 300	64	C ₂₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂	10.26	10.07	—
6.*	H	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	> 300	52	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂	9.43	9.74	—
7.*	Br	H	C ₆ H ₅	170	68	C ₂₇ H ₁₈ BrN ₂ O	8.91	8.75	Inactive
8.*	Br	H	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	192	70	C ₂₇ H ₁₇ BrClN ₂ O	8.52	8.16	25
9.	Br	H	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	184	70	C ₂₇ H ₁₇ BrClN ₂ O	7.80	8.16	65
10.	Br	H	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	198	65	C ₂₇ H ₁₆ BrN ₂ O ₂	8.94	8.47	—
11.	Br	H	<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	196	55	C ₂₇ H ₁₆ BrN ₂ O ₂	8.32	8.47	—
12.	Br	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	180	52	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ BrN ₂ O ₂	8.64	8.23	—
13.	Cl	H	C ₆ H ₅	130	48	C ₂₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O	9.31	9.64	—
14.	Cl	H	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	162	50	C ₂₇ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₂ O	8.68	8.94	12
15.	Cl	H	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	144	48	C ₂₇ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₂ O	8.62	8.94	—
16.	Cl	H	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	200	60	C ₂₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂	9.66	9.30	90
17.	Cl	H	<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	176	58	C ₂₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂	9.00	9.30	30
18.	Cl	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	184	55	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ O ₂	9.41	9.02	—
19.	I	H	C ₆ H ₅	235	62	C ₂₇ H ₁₈ IN ₂ O	7.64	7.97	—
20.	I	H	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	220	46	C ₂₇ H ₁₇ ClIN ₂ O	7.82	7.48	55
21.	I	H	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	198	50	C ₂₇ H ₁₇ ClIN ₂ O	7.06	7.48	—
22.	I	H	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	242	52	C ₂₇ H ₁₆ IN ₂ O ₂	8.00	7.73	54.1
23.	I	H	<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	224	46	C ₂₇ H ₁₆ IN ₂ O ₂	7.42	7.73	—
24.	I	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	98	54	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ IN ₂ O ₂	7.28	7.54	—
25.	Br	Br	C ₆ H ₅	130	60	C ₂₇ H ₁₇ Br ₂ N ₂ O	7.16	7.51	—
26.	Br	Br	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	177	64	C ₂₇ H ₁₆ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O	7.40	7.08	51.3
27.	Br	Br	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	180	44	C ₂₇ H ₁₆ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O	7.39	7.08	—
28.	Br	Br	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	184	50	C ₂₇ H ₁₇ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂	7.58	7.30	64.9
29.	Br	Br	<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	148	68	C ₂₇ H ₁₇ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂	7.02	7.30	42.2
30.	Br	Br	<i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	218	70	C ₂₈ H ₁₉ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂	7.46	7.13	—

* Showed spectral bands at 1680-1670 cm⁻¹ (N=CH-).

The screening results are recorded in the Table 2.

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Discussion

Thirteen compounds (Table 2), when screened against *H. nana* infection in mice at a dose of 250 mg/kg showed activity upto 90%. It was observed that the maximum activity was exhibited when OH in R was *o*-substituted. The activity was decreased when OH was *p*-substituted or replaced by Cl or H. Moreover, the presence of halogen in the phenyl nucleus of the quinazolone moiety was also essential for the activity in these compounds.

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